

1 Xist activation and repression is linked to double strand breaks and transmission synthesis associated with
2 replication stress or stalled forks by activation of PHF2, PHF8 and PHF20.

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4 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
5 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
6 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
7 East Islip, NY USA 11730

8 We identified factors responsible for activation of Xist expression from the endogenous Xist locus following
9 DNA damage, including double strand breaks and replication stress, like that which occurs when BRCA1,
10 Rif1 and MRE11A are depleted.

11 We found that PHF2/8/20 were each co-regulated with Xist localization factors SPEN and Ciz1. Further
12 evidence of interaction between specific Phf factors and Xist was co-regulation of PHF2/8/20 with Xist
13 RNP components PHF20a and SAFB. Indeed, PHF2/8/20 are co-regulated with Xist.

14 DNA damage caused by exposure to the mutagen MMS resulted in PHF2/8/20 induction. DNA damage
15 caused by exposure to ionizing radiation (IR) resulted in PHF2/8/20 induction. Double strand breaks
16 resulting from Rag2 deficiency resulted in PHF2/8/20 induction. Double strand breaks resulting from
17 Artemis (DCLRE1C) deficiency also resulted in PHF2/8/20 induction.
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